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Research Article

**AWARENESS OF ORAL HYGIENE AND DENTAL CARRIES
AMONG MALE STUDENTS OF LAHORE MEDICAL AND
DENTAL COLLEGE*****Dr. Farwa Waheed, *Dr. Mehwish Mazhar, *Dr. Saman Zahra**
*De'Montmorency College of Dentistry, Lahore Pakistan**Abstract:**

Objective: The objective of the present study was to determine caries experience, oral hygiene status and practices in male dental students.

Study Design: A Cross-Sectional Study.

Place and Duration: This study was conducted in male students of Lahore Medical and Dental College for one year duration from July 2017 to July 2018.

Methods: A total of 211 male undergraduate dental students were examined for dental caries and oral hygiene. The information about oral hygiene practices was obtained through a self-administered questionnaire. The prevalence of caries was 95.3%. Mean decayed, missing and filled (DMFT) score in the dental students was 7.97 (SD 4.64) with decay (D) component of 3.59 (SD 3.88), missing (M) component of 0.67 (SD 1.29) and filled component of 3.71 (SD 3.89).

Results: There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between the mean DMFT scores of the students from various academic levels. Only one-fifth (20.9%) of the students had good oral hygiene. The percentage of students with poor oral hygiene significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased as the academic level increased. The use of toothbrush significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased through senior academic levels, with a majority cleaning their teeth either once (33.2%) or twice (35.1%) daily.

Conclusion: It can be concluded that the caries prevalence and severity among the dental students was very high. Only a small percentage of the students had good oral hygiene.

Key words: Oral hygiene, dental students, carries, decay.

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INTRODUCTION:

University students are an important part of a society. They are role models for a society and future leaders in their fields. Health science students, including dental students, have an important role in structuring health-related behavior in their patients. Dental health behaviors of dental students play an important role in promoting good oral health in future patients. A general decrease in the frequency of dental caries has been reported in most Western countries. In contrast, many studies in Pakistan reported a high incidence of caries among schoolchildren. There is no specific study on the frequency of caries in Pakistani university students. However, a high prevalence of caries is expected among university students, including dental students, because students with high decay experience attend university. For some time, a relationship has been established between poor oral hygiene and gingival / periodontal disease. The relationship between poor oral hygiene and tooth decay has also been reported. Motivating and providing oral hygiene instructions to patients is one of the tasks for dentistry students. It will be interesting to determine the oral hygiene status and practices of dental students and to have a difference between students in different academic level.

The aims of this study were to determine: Oral hygiene status and applications to dental students and If there is a difference between the experience of caries and students at various academic levels related to state / oral hygiene practices.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This Cross-Sectional study was conducted in male students of Lahore Medical and Dental College for one year duration from July 2017 to July 2018. All male dentistry students in the male campus of Lahore Medical and Dental College were examined for tooth decay and oral hygiene. WHO criteria were used for the diagnosis of tooth decay (WHO 1997). Oral hygiene status was evaluated by *James et al* recommendations. In three categories using oral hygiene oral hygiene index; well, fair and poor. Information about oral hygiene practices was

obtained through a self-administered questionnaire. The following data were collected by survey. Students' demographic information age and academic level.

Toothbrush, misvak (traditional wooden toothbrush) etc. As used in oral hygiene tools and the frequency of tooth cleaning. One of the researchers (EAA) studied a student in a dental chair using a mirror and an explorer. The examiner was calibrated with a superior faculty and the internal and external auditor reliability was determined. The data obtained by the review were recorded in a form specially designed for the study. The data were then entered into a computer using the FOXPRO software and analyzed using the Statistical Program for Social Sciences (SPSS version-18). ANOVA was used to test the difference between the mean DMFT scores of various academic levels. Chi-square tests were used to verify the difference between various academic levels in terms of state and oral hygiene practices.

RESULTS:

A total of 211 male students who completed the study in 2017-2018 participated in the study. There were 61 students in the first year, 50 in the second year, 33 in the third year, 40 in the fourth year and 27 students in the BDS class of the last year. Internal and patient reliability for dental caries were 0.85 and 0.89, respectively, according to Kappa statistics. The reliability of oral hygiene examinations was found to be 0.84 according to the Kappa statistics. The frequency of caries in the study population was 95.3% and the mean DMFT score was 7.97 (SD 4.64) with a 3.59 (SD 3.64) dissociation component (D) a missing component (M) of 0.67 (SD 1.29) and a packed component of 3.71 SD 3.89). There was no significant difference in the mean DMFT scores of the students at various academic levels (Table 1). However, the proportion of the fragmentation component of the mean score of the DMFT was significantly lower among the higher dental students ($p < .05$) (Table 1). On the other hand, the ratio of the filling component of the mean DMFT score increased significantly at academic levels ($p < 0.05$) (Table 1).

Academic Level	Mean DMFT (SD)	Mean Decay (SD)	Mean Filled (SD)
1 st year	7.11(5.10)	4.25(4.3)	2.2(3.17)
2 nd year	8.38(4.67)	5.00(4.07)	2.8(3.46)
3 rd year	7.06(3.82)	2.45(2.81)	3.94(3.52)
4 th year	9.10(4.35)	2.93(3.58)	5.65(4.42)
5 th year	8.56(4.55)	1.89(2.95)	5.56(4.39)

TABLE 1: CARIES EXPERIENCE OF THE DENTAL STUDENTS

The missing component of the mean DMFT score was very small for all academic levels and did not change significantly with academic levels ($p > 0.05$). Only one fifth (20.9%) of the students had good oral hygiene (Table 2).

Academic Level	Oral Hygiene Status		
	Good (%)	Fair (%)	Poor (%)
1 st year	13(23.2)	21(37.5)	22(39.3)
2 nd year	10(20.0)	19(38.0)	21(42.0)
3 rd year	3(9.1)	29(87.9)	1(3.0)
4 th year	7(17.5)	27(67.5)	6(15.0)
5 th year	10(37.0)	13(48.1)	4(4.8)
Total	43(20.9)	109(52.9)	54(26.2)

TABLE 2: ORAL HYGIENE STATUS OF THE DENTAL STUDENTS.

The majority of the students in the first year (76.8%) had poor or fair oral hygiene compared to the elderly (86.1%) who had fair or good oral hygiene (Table 2). The use of dental floss was also significantly higher among older students than the third grade students ($p < .05$) (Table 3).

Academic Level	Oral Hygiene Methods			
	Brush Only (%)	Brush & Miswak (%)	Miswak Only (%)	Dental Floss (%)
1 st year	32(52.5)	24(39.3)	7(1.5)	9(4.8)
2 nd year	23(48.9)	20(42.6)	6(12.8)	11(23.4)
3 rd year	24(75.0)	7(21.9)	1(3.1)	14(43.8)
4 th year	31(79.5)	8(20.5)	4(10.3)	24(61.5)
5 th year	20(74.1)	6(22.2)	3(11.1)	18(66.7)

TABLE 3: VARIOUS ORAL HYGIENE METHODS USED BY THE DENTAL STUDENTS.

Most students cleaned their teeth once a day (33.2%) or twice a day (35.1%), and only one in ten (9.3%) brushed their teeth three times a day (Table 4).

Academic Level	Frequency of Tooth Cleaning					
	Once (%)	Twice (%)	Thrice (%)	>3 times (%)	Sometime (%)	Total (%)
1st year	19(31.1)	17(27.9)	1(1.6)	2(3.3)	22(36.1)	61(100)
2 nd year	18(38.3)	9(19.1)	6(12.8)	2(4.3)	12(25.5)	47(100)
3 rd year	11(34.4)	14(43.8)	5(15.6)	2(6.3)	–	32(100)
4 th year	13(34.2)	17(44.7)	5(13.2)	1(2.6)	2(5.3)	38(100)
5 th year	7(25.9)	15(55.6)	2(7.4)	2(7.4)	1(3.7)	27(100)
Total	68(33.2)	72(35.1)	19(9.3)	9(4.4)	37(18.0)	205(100)

TABLE 4: FREQUENCY OF TOOTH CLEANING AMONG THE STUDENTS.

DISCUSSION:

This study provided an interesting insight into the experience of caries and the practice of caries and state / oral hygiene. The results will be useful in motivating students to improve oral health conditions and practices. These results will also serve as key data for future comparisons. In this study, dental patients had a very high tooth decay experience. However, this result was not unexpected. Recent studies by Pakistani school children reported that there was a very high level of caries experience and school children were taking diseases to universities. However, such a high level of caries experience is worrying. Schools in Saudi Arabia have identified difficulties in the prevalence and severity of caries and urgent measures have been demanded to increase preventive efforts among schoolchildren. The proportion of the impairment component of the DMFT score decreased at academic levels. Students are probably thought to regain their decayed teeth because of their awareness of the disease and the importance of treatment. A recent study of Tunisian dentistry students showed a similar trend. A study of Danish dental students has also identified better oral health during the academic year. Dental students are expected to have better oral health than other young people of similar age. There is no current data comparing Saudi dentist students to another Saudi population of similar age. However, studies in other countries have shown results in favor of dental students. In this study, few dental students had good oral hygiene. However, the percentage of people with good oral hygiene increased to the highest academic level. However, an improvement is expected as a result of awareness gained through preventive dentistry courses and peer interaction. The use of the brush and waste combination has declined significantly throughout the academic year. This trend can be attributed to the traditional education of preventive dentistry, which puts great emphasis on the use of the toothbrush to clean the teeth. A number

of studies have been reported on the utility of dental hygiene. The most important thing is to historically promote the wrong and widespread use of religious and cultural hygiene rules. Increasing the use of floss among the highest academic levels can be attributed to the increase in the number of teeth restored in the mouth, which requires greater awareness of oral hygiene and cleansing of interproximal regions. A response obtained through the questionnaire should be considered to a certain degree. In this study, questions about oral hygiene practices were a sensitive area for a dental student and could not eliminate the possibility of a bias created by a positive response.

CONCLUSION:

The prevalence and severity of dental caries were very high among male dental students. Only one fifth of the study population had good oral hygiene; The proportion of people with high oral hygiene increased at high academic levels. The proportion of the completed component of the mean DMFT score was significantly higher at higher academic levels.

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